

SHORT NOTES

Use of Cation-exchange Resins as Catalyst in
Pechmann Reaction

K. N. Trivedi

Out of several methods for synthesising coumarins¹, the Pechmann reaction², consisting of condensation of phenol with a β -ketonic ester, is considered to be the most convenient. In this reaction, the choice of a proper condensing agent plays a very important part. Sulphuric acid, phosphorus pentoxide, phosphorus oxychloride, anhydrous aluminium chloride, zinc chloride, cation-exchange resins^{3,4}, and others have been employed extensively to bring about the condensation. In view of this, it was thought of interest to investigate the role of different cation-exchange resins in the condensation of β -ketonic esters with phenols.

Reactive phenols, such as resorcinol, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol, and α -naphthol, have been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate, using Duolite C-20 and Amberlite IR-120, polystyrene sulphonic acid type resins, and corresponding coumarin derivatives obtained in good yields. Attempts to condense less reactive phenols, such as methyl β -resorcyate, resacetophenone, β -naphthol, with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of the above resins did not succeed. Attempts to condense resorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of Duolite CS-101, a cation-exchange resin with exchangeable hydrogen ion in a carboxyl group, and Amberlite IRA-400, an anion-exchange resin, did not succeed.

TABLE I

Phenol.	β -Ketonic ester.	Coumarin formed.	*M.P.	%Yield.
Resorcinol	Ethyl acetoacetate	7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin	186°	69
	Ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate	7-Hydroxy-3, 4-dimethylcoumarin	256°	50
Pyrogallol	Ethyl acetoacetate	7, 8-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin	232°	38
Phloroglucinol	Do	5,7-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin	282°	48
α -Naphthol	Do	4-Methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin	170°	57

*Mixed m.p.s with authentic specimens were not depressed.

1. Sethna and Shah, *Chem. Rev.*, 1945, **36**, 1.
2. Sethna and Pbadke, "Organic Reactions", Vol, VII, p. 1.
3. John and Israelstam, *Chem. Ind.*, 1958, 1262.
4. *Idem*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 240.

General Procedure.—A mixture of reactive phenol, β -ketonic ester, and Doulite C-20 (30% of the total weight of the mixture) was heated in an oil bath at 150° with occasional stirring. In the first 15 min. the reaction product started solidifying. The reaction mixture was further heated for 45 min. to complete the reaction. To the cooled reaction mixture sufficient ethanol was added and the mixture refluxed. It was then filtered hot to remove the resin. The filtrate on cooling provided the product. The coumarins, thus prepared, are recorded in Table I.

Thanks are due to Professor Suresh Sethna for his valuable guidance during the course of this work.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
M. S. UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODA-2.

Received March 12, 1964.